

ISic1516

I.Sicily inscription 1516

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Catacomb of S.Giovanni

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 14600

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Εὐσκία ἢ ἄμειντος ζή(σ)α(σα)
2. χρηστῶς καὶ σεμνῶς ἔτη
3. πλῖο(ν) ἔλαττον κε ἄνε
4. παύσετο τῆ ἐορτῆ τῆς κυ
5. ρίας μου Λουκίας εἰς ἧν
6. οὐκ ἐστιν ἐνκώμιον
7. εἰπεῖν χρηστειανή πισ
8. τή τέλιος οὔσα εὐχα
9. ριστοῦσα τῷ εἰδ[ίωάν]
10. δρὶ πολλὰς εὐχαρισ
11. τίας α □ ω ε[---] εὐτυ[χοίης]

Apparatus

Text based on photograph

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645016

PHI 333765

Bibliography

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